

Research Article

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EFFECT OF PROCESSING ON THE *IN VITRO* PROTEIN, CARBOHYDRATE DIGESTIBILITY AND ANTINUTRITIONAL FACTORS ON DAN WAKE COMPOSITE FLOUR MADE FROM COWPEA (*Triticum aestivum*), BAMBARA NUT (*Vigna unguiculata* L.), (*Voandzeia subterranean* L.) AND CASSAVA (*Mannihot esculentus*)

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ABSTRACT

The traditional food system is all food from a particular culture produced from local sources which people culturally accept. The production and evaluation of the nutritional qualities of three high energy/protein meals ('dan wake') formulated from blends of germinated wheat, dehulled cowpea and dehulled Bambara nut, and Fermented cassava flour were studied. The different ingredients used were, sprouted wheat, dehulled cowpea and Bambara nut, fermented cassava, baobab leaves (kuka), and potash (kanwa) were incorporated in the proportion of 70:17:4:4:3.5:1.5 for composite 'dan wake' flour test 1 Aa. The ratios 60:15:5: 16:3:1 is for composite flour test 2 Bb, and 9:18:9:60:3:1 for composite 'dan wake' flour test 3 Cc respectively. A control 'dan wake' flour wheat flour 100% (WWF) and cassava flour 100% (CCF) served as control. The following parameters were assayed using standard laboratory methods. These include; *in vitro* protein and carbohydrate digestibility, and antinutritional factors. Results of the *in vitro* protein and carbohydrate digestibility show a significant ($P < 0.05$) increase in all the samples after processing, while that of the antinutritional factors were significantly (< 0.05) reduced after processing. For the composite dan wake flours, in terms of *in vitro* protein and carbohydrate digestibility, samples Aa and Bb recorded the highest values compared to the control samples and Cc. In conclusion, from the results obtained, the processing method employed has significantly reduced the antinutritional contents of all the dan wake formulations, thereby leading to improved protein and carbohydrate digestibility of the formulations. However, among the dan wake formulations, Aa and Bb are superior in terms of protein and carbohydrate digestibility compared to the control composite dan wake flour.

Keywords Dan wake; Bambara nut; Cassava; Cowpea; Antinutritional

INTRODUCTION

The traditional food system is all food from a particular culture produced from local sources that are culturally accepted by the people. It includes socio-cultural meanings, acquisition, processing techniques, usage, composition, and nutritional consequences for people using the food [1]. It refers to human, managed biophysical systems that are involved in the production, distribution, and consumption of food in a particular environment [2].

Undernutrition, including micro-nutrient deficiencies, is the leading risk factor for disease and death worldwide accounting for over half the disease burden in developing countries and poor combination of the various foods is the bane of adequate nutrient intake. Food systems are a natural locus for improving nutritional security in societies hence, when properly prepared and combined; Nigerian traditional food can assume nutrition security in all segments of society [2].

Breakfast meals in Africa particularly Northern Nigeria for both adults and infants are based on local staple diets made from tubers, cereals, and legumes [3]. However, most cereals are limited in essential amino acids such as tryptophan, although some are rich in lysine [4]. Tubers such as Cassava are poor in protein [5], while legumes are rich in essential amino acids, particularly sulphur amino acids [3].

Thus, a combination of such foodstuffs will improve the nutritional value of the resulting blend which makes it better compared to the individual components alone [6]. Traditional foods of northern Nigerian origin are including: “dan wake”, ‘Nakiya’, ‘pate-pate’, ‘Sinahir’, ‘Akamu’, ‘Masa’, ‘Dambu’ [7], ‘Moi-moi’, ‘Kosai’ which are produced from legumes, tubers, and cereals. “Dan wake” is a popular breakfast meal in northern Nigeria, prepared either from cassava flour and wheat flour or cassava flour and cowpea flour as a dumpling. Different proportions and combinations of cassava flour, cowpea flour, or wheat flour are used. Baobab leaves and potash are added during preparation. Groundnut oil and seasoning are added to the cooked “dan wake”. Traditional foods based on cereals or tubers have to undergo modification to warrant a balance in essential nutrients. Many cereal-legume combinations have been found to provide supplementary effect on the protein/amino acid profile of the combined composition [8]. The chief ingredient in “dan wake” is cassava flour (lafun) which is poor in terms of protein contents [5]. The traditional breakfast meals for both adults and children in Northern Nigeria are based on staple diets made mostly from mono tubers and mono cereals, especially cassava and wheat which are of low nutritional quality and high energy density leading to nutritional imbalances such as obesity, undernutrition and micronutrient deficiencies. Thus, this informed the production and formulation of high protein meal from wheat, cassava, Bambara nut, and cowpea.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Sources of Materials

The cassava was obtained from Bichi L.G.A. of Kano state, and Bambara nut and baobab leaves were obtained from the Maiduguri Monday market. Improved variety of the cowpea (banjara) was obtained in Maiduguri Metropolis through Borno State Agricultural Development Program (BOSADP) and improved wheat variety (Seri M82) was obtained from Lake Chad Research Institute (LCRI). The cereals, legumes, and tubers were authenticated by a seed breeder at the Lake Chad Research Institute Maiduguri and a plant taxonomist from the Department of Biological Sciences University of Maiduguri.

Methods

Preparation of Cassava Flour

The fresh cassava roots were peeled, washed, steeped in water for 3 days, and pulped. The cassava pulp was pressed using a screw press to reduce the water contents. The pressed pulp was dried using a LEEC cabinet dryer at 60°C for 2 days to obtain a constant moisture content of 8% and then milled into fine flour [9], while fermentation was excluded for the unprocessed cassava flour.

Preparation of cowpea flour

Five hundred grams (500g) of cowpea was sorted, cleaned of dirt, soaked in water for 5 minutes, and then dehulled using mortar and pestle. The dehulled seeds were dried to a constant weight, milled, and then sieved with a 5mm pore sieve to obtain fine flour [10]. Five hundred grams (500g) of the cowpea was sorted, cleaned of dirt, milled, and sieved with a 5mm pore sieve to obtain the unprocessed cowpea flour.

Preparation of Bambara nut Flour

Five hundred grams (500g) of Bambara nut was sorted, cleaned of dirt, and soaked in water overnight. It was then dehulled, drained, and dried to a moisture content of about 7- 8 %, and then sieved using a 5mm pore sieve into a fine powder [11]. Five hundred grams (500g) of dry Bambara nut was sorted, cleaned, and sieved using a 5mm pore sieve to obtain the unprocessed Bambara nut flour.

Preparation of wheat flour

The grains were sprouted as described by [12]. About 500g of the wheat samples were soaked in a plastic bucket containing 300 ml of distilled water and steeped for one hour at room temperature (28± 2°C). The steeped water was discarded by decantation and the grains were germinated for 72 hours by spreading on a clean grease-free tray pan thereafter, it was sun-dried for 2-3 days by putting in a sterilized tray pan. The wheat grains were milled using a disc attrition mill (hunt No.2A Premier Mill Hunt and Co, UK) to an average particle size of less than 0.3mm. The mill grain was then sieved through a fine mesh (5mm) to obtain the wheat flour. Five hundred grams (500g) of wheat was sorted and cleaned of dirt, milled, and sieved using a 5mm pore sieve to obtain the unprocessed wheat flour.

Scheme I: Flow Chart showing the preparation of processed sample Formulation of Composite “dan wake” flour

Scheme 1: Flow diagram for the preparation of processed sample Formulation of Composite “dan wake” flour

Table 1: Formulation of Composite “dan wake” Flours (g)

Formulations	PWF	PCF	PBF	WWF	CCF	Potash	Baobab	Total
Aa	70	16	4	-	4	2	4	100
Bb	60	15	15	-	4	2	4	100
Cc	9	18	9	-	60	2	4	100
WWF	-	-	-	94	-	2	4	100
CCF	-	-	-	-	94	2	4	100

Key: PWF= Processed wheat flour; PCF= Processed cowpea flour; PBF= Processed Bambara nut flour; CCF= Cassava flour; WWF= White wheat flour

Determination of *in Vitro* Protein Digestibility

The method described by [14] was adopted for this study. One milliliter (1mL) of 11% trypsin was introduced into 16 test tubes and 1mL of 0.1% NaCl was added and allowed to stand to equilibrate, 1ml of “dan wake” blend mixture was added to all the test tubes (labeled as digestibility at 1 hour and 6 hours). The reaction in each of the test tubes was stopped with 5ml of neutralized formalin at 60 minutes and 6 hours. The content of the test tube was then filtered using filter paper. The filter papers were dried in an oven at 108°C for 3 hours. The nitrogen of the undigested sample was determined by the Kjeldahl method.

$$\% \text{ in vitro protein digestibility} = \frac{CP_1 - CP_2}{CP_1} \times 100$$

Where

CP1=Total protein of unprocessed grain; CP2=Total protein after digestion with trypsin

Determination of Antinutritional Factors of the Samples

Determination of Phytate Content of the Samples by Method

Four grams (4g) of the sample was soaked in 100 cm³ of 2% HCl for 3 hours and then filtered through two layers of filter paper. The filtrate (25cm³) was placed in a 250cm³ conical flask and 5cm³ of 0.3 % NH₄SCN solution was added as an indicator. Fifty-three centimeter cube (53.0cm³) of distilled water was added to reach the proper acidity. This mixture was titrated against FeCl₃ solution, which contains about 0.00195 g of Fe per cm³ of FeCl₃ solution. The result was multiplied by factor 1.95 to obtain Phytate P. Phytate P result was multiplied by factor 3.55 to convert to Phytate [15].

Determination of Cyanide Contents of the Samples

Cyanide was determined by the alkaline picrate method of [16]. The known sample was weighed and the cyanide sample was extracted, an alkaline picrate solution was prepared and the cyanide content of the sample was determined.

Extraction of Samples for Cyanide Determination

Five (5) grams of the sample were ground into a paste. The paste dissolved in 50 mL distilled water in a corked conical flask, and the cyanide extract was allowed to stay overnight. The extract was then filtered and the filtrate was used for the cyanide determination.

Preparation of Alkaline Picrate Solution

One gram (1g) of picrate and five gram (5) of sodium carbonate were dissolved in a volume of minimally warm water. The volume makes up to 200ml with distilled water.

Procedure for cyanide Determination

To 1mL of the sample filtrate in a corked test, 4 mL of alkaline picrate was added and incubated in a water bath at 40°C for five minutes. After colour development, the absorbance of the corked test tube was read in a spectrophotometer at 490nm. The absorbance of the blank containing only one (1) milliliter of distilled water and 4 mL alkaline picrate was also read. The cyanide content was extrapolated from a cyanide standard curve.

Preparation of Calibration Curve for Cyanide standards

Different concentrations of KCN solution containing 5-50µg cyanide were prepared in a 500 mL conical flask. Twenty-five (25) milliliters of 1N HCl was added. The cyanide standard curve was prepared using different concentrations.

RESULTS

In vitro protein digestibility

Table 2 presents the *in vitro* protein digestibility of the unprocessed and processed samples. Significant (P<0.05) increases in digestibility at 1 hour and 6 hours were observed in all the samples. The processed samples had higher digestibility than the unprocessed samples. Germinated wheat had the highest digestibility (27.31±0.01%) at 1 hour, while dehulled cowpea had the highest digestibility (50.20±0.01 %) at 6 hours.

Table 3 presents the *in vitro* protein digestibility of composite ‘dan wake’ flours. The composite ‘dan wake’ flour (Bb) had a digestibility of 31.1±0.01 % at 1 hour, this value when compared with the other blends is the highest, and significantly (p<0.05) different, and also when compared with the control groups CCF and WWF. The food blend Cc

recorded the least digestibility at 1 hour. The result of digestibility at 6 hours shows that, the digestibility of composite 'dan wake' flours significantly ($P<0.05$) increased after 6 hours. However, the food blend Bb recorded the highest value of 42.62, while Cc recorded the lowest value of digestibility at 6 hours.

Table 2: *In vitro* protein digestibility of unprocessed and processed samples of wheat, cowpea, Bambara nut, and cassava

	Sample							
	Wheat		Cowpea		Bambara nut		Cassava	
Digestibility	Unprocessed	Germinated	processed	Dehulled	Unprocessed	Dehulled	unprocessed	fermented
1 hr(%)	40±0.21 ^a	31±0.01 ^b	61±21 ^a	11±0.01 ^b	21±0.01 ^a	20±0.02 ^b	22±0.01 ^a	54±0.01 ^a
6hrs (%)	30±0.11 ^a	30±0.21 ^b	60±0.10 ^a	20±0.01 ^b	60±0.01 ^a	30±004 ^b	50±0.01 ^a	77±0.01 ^b

Values are mean ±SEM, n=3; Values with different superscripts along the row are statistically significant ($P<0.05$)

Table 3: *In vitro* protein digestibility of composite "dan wake" flours produced from wheat, cowpea, Bambara nut, and cassava

Digestibility	Aa	Bb	Cc	CCF	WWF
1hr (%)	21.89±0.01 ^a	31.11±0.01 ^b	16.32±0.01 ^c	10.54±0.01 ^d	23.50±0.01 ^e
6hrs (%)	33.85±0.01 ^a	42.62±0.01 ^b	19.44±0.02 ^c	10.77±0.01 ^d	33.61±0.01 ^e

Values are mean ± SEM, n =3; Values with different superscripts along the column are significantly different ($P<0.05$); Kay: Aa = 70% PWF with 16%PCF, 4%CCF, 4%PBF, 2% potash and 4%baobab leaves; Bb = 60% PWF with 15%PCF, 4%CCF, 15%PBF, 2% potash and 4% baobab leaves; Cc = 60% CCF with 18%PCF, 9%PBF, 9%PWF, 2 potash and 4%baobab leaves; CCF= cassava flour; WWF= white wheat flour; CCF= cassava flour; PWF=processed wheat flour

***In Vitro* Carbohydrate Digestibility**

Table 4 presents the *in vitro* carbohydrate digestibility of the unprocessed and processed samples. A significant ($P<0.05$) increase in digestibility at 1 hour and 6 hours was observed in all the samples. The processed samples had higher digestibility than the unprocessed samples. Germinated wheat had higher digestibility (0.36±0.02) at 30 min and (0.42-0.01) at 1 hour, while fermented cassava had the highest digestibility at 6 hours (0.66±0.01).

Table 5 presents the result of *in vitro* carbohydrate digestibility at 30 minutes, 1 hour, and 6 hours for the different formulated food blends. A significant increase was recorded in digestibility at 1 hour when compared with the results of digestibility at 30 minutes. The differences were statistically significant ($P <0.05$). Digestibility at 6 hours had higher values for all the food blends when compared with digestibility at 1 hour and 30 minutes for all the food blends. The food blend supplemented with 60% processed wheat flour (Bb) recorded a higher digestibility of 0.09 at 30 minutes, and 0.65 at 1 hour. However, the food blend supplemented with 70% processed wheat flour (Aa) had a higher value for digestibility (0.80) at 6 hours.

Table 4: *In vitro* carbohydrate digestibility of unprocessed and processed samples of wheat, cowpea, Bambara nut, and cassava

	Samples							
	Wheat		Cowpea		Bambara nut		Cassava	
digestibility	unprocessed	germinated	unprocessed	Dehulled	unprocessed	dehulled	unprocessed	fermented
30min	0.30±0.00 ^a	0.36±0.02 ^b	0.20±0.01 ^a	0.30±0.02 ^a	0.10±0.01 ^a	0.15±0.01 ^a	0.28±0.01 ^a	0.25±0.01 ^a
1 hr	037±0.02 ^a	0.42±0.01 ^b	0.29±0.01 ^a	0.32±0.01 ^b	0.18±0.11 ^a	0.21±0.02 ^b	0.45±0.01 ^a	0.43±0.01 ^a
6hrs	0.49±0.03 ^a	0.57±0.21 ^b	0.40±0.01 ^a	0.50±0.02 ^a	0.22±0.01 ^a	0.27±0.01 ^a	0.67±0.01 ^a	0.66±0.01 ^a

Values are mean \pm SEM, n=3; Values with different superscripts along the row are significantly different (P<0.05)

Table 5: *In vitro* carbohydrate digestibility of composite 'dan wake' flour produced from wheat, cowpea, Bambara nut, and cassava

Sample	30min	1hr	6hr
Aa	0.07 \pm 0.01 ^b	0.55 \pm 0.01 ^b	0.80 \pm 0.01 ^a
Bb	0.09 \pm 0.01 ^d	0.65 \pm 0.01 ^c	0.72 \pm 0.01 ^c
Cc	0.04 \pm 0.01 ^{fe}	0.10 \pm 0.01 ^e	0.40 \pm 0.01 ^{ed}
UCF	0.28 \pm 0.01 ^{hg}	0.45 \pm 0.01 ^{gf}	0.66 \pm 0.01 ^g
WWF	0.08 \pm 0.02 ^{ib}	0.15 \pm 0.01 ^h	0.67 \pm 0.01 ^{hg}

Values are mean \pm SEM, n=3; Values with different superscripts along the column are significantly different (P<0.05)

Key: Aa = 70% PWF with 16%PCF, 4%CCF, 4%PBF, 2% potash and 4%baobab leaves; Bb = 60% PWF with 15%PCF, 4%CCF, 15%PBF, 2% potash and 4% baobab leaves; Cc = 60% CCF with 18%PCF, 9%PBF, 9%PWF, 2 potash and 4%baobab leaves CCF= cassava flour; WWF= white wheat flour; PWF=processed wheat flour; PCF= Processed cowpea flour; PBF= processed Bambara nut flour

Antinutritional factors

The results for antinutritional factors of the raw and processed wheat, cowpea, Bambara nut, and cassava flour are shown in Table 6. A significant (P <0.05) decrease in the phytic acid was observed in germinated wheat, dehulled cowpea, and Bambara nuts. A reduction of 69%, 71%, and 78.5 % was observed in the phytic acid contents of germinated wheat, dehulled cowpea, and Bambara nut respectively. Significant (P <0.05) reduction in the cyanide contents of fermented cassava also significant (P <0.05) reduction of 84.8% respectively.

The results of the antinutritional contents of food blends are presented in Table 7. The phytic acid content of Cc was higher with a value of 1.03. Compared to Aa (0.80) and Bb (0.86). The differences were significant (P <0.05). The phytic contents of the control blend CCF were higher when compared with the test blends, and with the control WWF, the differences were significant (P <0.05). The cyanide contents of the blends Aa, Bb, and Cc were 1.40, 1.52, and 1.97 respectively. The differences were significant. The control CCF had higher cyanide content when compared with the blends and the control WWF.

Table 6: Antinutrient contents of unprocessed and processed samples of wheat, cowpea, Bambara nut, and cassava

	Samples							
	Wheat		Cassava		Cowpea		Bambara nut	
	Unprocessed	Fermented	Unprocessed	Fermented	Unprocessed	Dehulled	Unprocessed	Dehulled
Phytic(mg/g)	0.49 \pm 0.02 ^a	0.09 \pm 0.01 ^b	NA	NA	0.59 \pm 0.02 ^a	0.10 \pm 0.01 ^b	0.96 \pm 0.02 ^a	0.34 \pm 0.02 ^b
% decrease	69.0		NA	NA	71.0		78.5	
Cyanide	NA	NA	3.02 \pm 0.01 ^a	1.15 \pm 0.01 ^b	NA	NA	NA	NA
% decrease	NA	NA	84.8		NA	NA	NA	NA

Values are mean \pm SEM, n=3; Values with different superscripts along the row are significantly different (P<0.05); Key: NA= Not applicable

Table 7: Antinutrient factors of composite ‘‘dan wake’’ flour blends produced from wheat, cowpea, Bambara nut, and cassava

Samples	Phytic acid(mg/g)	Cyanide(mg HCN/kg)
Aa	0.50±0.01 ^a	1.40±0.02 ^a
Bb	0.86±0.02 ^b	1.52±0.02 ^b
Cc	1.03±0.01 ⁺	1.97±0.01 ^c
CCF	1.50±0.03 ^d	2.89±0.01 ^d
WWF	0.61±0.01 ^a	-

Values are mean ± SEM, n =3; Values with different superscripts along the column are significantly different (P<0.05)

Keys= Aa = 70% PWF with 16%PCF, 4%CCF, 4%PBF, 2% potash and 4%baobab leaves; Bb = 60% PWF with 15%PCF, 4%CCF, 15%PBF, 2% potash and 4% baobab leaves; Cc = 60% CCF with 18%PCF, 9%PBF, 9%PWF, 2% potash and 4%baobab leaves; WWF= white wheat flour; CCF= cassava flour; PWF=processed wheat flour; PCF= Processed cowpea flour; PBF= processed Bambara nut flour

DISCUSSION

The processing methods germination, fermentation, and dehulling of wheat, cassava, cowpea, and Bambara nut respectively increased the digestibility of processed samples, and that of the composite ‘dan wake’ flours Aa, Bb Cc, this might be due to the reduction in antinutrient factors during processing [19]. The increase in *in vitro* protein digestibility might be due to the activity of the proteolytic enzymes fermentation/ germination which degrades protein into samples protein, polypeptides, and amino acids, thus enhancing the digestibility of food samples as reported by [20] and [21]. Supplementation of the wheat with legumes may improve the protein contents of food blends as reported by [22].

The increase in *in vitro* carbohydrate digestibility observed may be a result of the processing methods, particularly fermentation. This results in the degradation of starch into smaller fragments and the formation of reducing sugar [23, 24]. The process of fermentation and germination leads to changes in the endosperm protein fractions and makes starch more accessible to the digestive enzyme [21]. The increased carbohydrate digestibility of the dehulled beans and Bambara nut may be due to the processing (Dehulling) which leads to a decrease in the antinutrient content thereby making the bioavailability of starchy components of the samples. The digestibility of the composite ‘dan wake’ flours increases with time.

The reduction in the phytic acid contents during germination of the wheat sample could be attributed to inherent phytase activity in the wheat which may hydrolyze phytic acid thereby reducing the phytic acid contents of germinated products [25]. The removal of the seed coat (dehulling) of soaked cowpea and Bambara nut may have been attributed to the reduction of the phytic acid content of the dehulled cowpea and Bambara nut. Soaking of cereals and legumes usually forms an integral part of processing methods such as germination, fermentation, and roasting [26].

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study demonstrate that the processing methods used have effectively reduced the levels of antinutritional compounds in all the dan wake formulations. This reduction has, in turn, led to a notable improvement in the digestibility of protein and carbohydrates in these formulations. A comparative analysis of the different dan wake formulations reveals that Aa and Bb exhibit superior protein and carbohydrate digestibility profiles compared to the control composite dan wake flours.

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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